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Abstract

The existence of anthropology as an academic and research discipline in Arunachal Pradesh is at infancy. The traditional ethnographic studies among the tribes were initiated by the early British administrators, missionaries, travellers, explorers, etc. Professor Furer-Haimendorf and Verrier Elwin were perhaps the first professional anthropologist and ethnographer to delve into the various cultural aspects of Arunachal tribes. The official recognition of the discipline took place with the introduction of Arunachal Institute of Tribal Studies (AITS) in 1995 under Arunachal University (Now Rajiv Gandhi University, Doimukh) which was established in 1984; for which anthropology – as a discipline – was introduced in 2001. The establishment of the Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh and introduction of Anthropology at the University and College levels significantly count towards the development of this discipline in the state. Research contributions have been witnessed over time in the field of social and cultural aspects of the tribes. Though not completely absent, researches on physical-biological aspects, genetic studies, linguistic and archaeology, growth, nutrition and health have been witnessed but limited. Taking into consideration the broad scope of Anthropology as a discipline of holistic approach, this paper urge for a need of wider coverage of studies in terms of research, projects, and publications in developing tribal state like Arunachal Pradesh. The relevance of Anthropology in the state could be ensured through rigorous research taken up at various levels of standard, support from the government, collaboration between academic institutions and funding agencies. At the same time, its dimension and scope as a relevant research and academic discipline

could be broadened and expanded through addressing new research questions, formulation of hypotheses, and through standard conduct of empirical researches.

Keywords: Anthropology, Ethnographic, Arunachal Pradesh, Arunachal Tribes, Research

Introduction

Arunachal Pradesh, one of the eight states of North East India occupies the largest geographical area (83,743 sq. km.) of the region and is located between 26.28° N and 29.30° N latitude and 91.20° E and 97.30° E longitude. The state is inhabited by as many as 26 major tribes and double or so number of sub-tribes which spreads over 25 districts. The population of Arunachal Pradesh – 1,382,611 people (Census of India, 2011) – is extremely heterogeneous in terms of peoples' culture, physical appearance, biology, language, religion, economy, political organization, etc., that makes the tribes to be distinct from one another. It may be noted that till 1972, Arunachal Pradesh was considered as a union territory of India - North Eastern Frontier Agency (NEFA) - by the Indian Government. Anthropologically speaking, the state may be considered as a true laboratory for many scholars who desire to delve the various anthropological issues ranging from human behaviours, cultural and social aspects of the people, life styles, their languages, religions, physical and biological set up of populations, genetics, archaeological studies and the like. Anthropology as a discipline of holistic understanding about humans would be of high significance in the context of Arunachal Pradesh and of great contribution to the understanding of the anthropological related issues of the tribes.

The existence of Anthropology as an academic and research discipline in North-east region in general – which in the not too distant past was commonly known as Assam – and in Arunachal Pradesh particularly, is at infancy. In Northeast, the traditional ethnographic studies among the hill tribes – though not highly empirical – were initiated by the early British administrators (e.g., Needham, Robinson, & Wilcox), soldiers (e.g., John Butler), missionaries (e.g., Nicholas Krick), tea planters (e.g., Grey), travellers (e.g., Thomas Cooper), explorers, etc. on the very fringe of Imperial India, before independence (Elwin, 1959). Outside of the administrators turned ethnographers, Professor Furer-Haimendorf was perhaps the first professional anthropologist to be commissioned by the government of Assam prior to Independence to explore the tribes of Subansiri district of Arunachal Pradesh (Furer-Haimendorf, 1955). In 1944, Haimendorf set off a temporary government outpost for the first time in Ziro which is located in the Lower Subansiri district of Arunachal Pradesh. Later researches took a slow pace to explore

this part of the country. In the 1950s, Verrier Elwin – as an Anthropological Advisor to the Governor of Assam - undertook extensive fieldwork in the vast and virgin terrains of Arunachal Pradesh, primarily focusing on the tribal affairs, their arts, myths, political systems, and history. Since the late 1950s, however, reports on number of Arunachal tribes have been prepared by other scholars as well.

Nevertheless, drawing on the origin and development of Anthropology in Arunachal Pradesh in terms of establishment of departments and research centres took place much later, of the early dates; after independence and the attainment of the statehood that happened on 20th February 1987.

Objectives

This paper aims at reviewing the genesis and status of anthropology as a discipline in terms of establishment of departments and research centres in the state of Arunachal Pradesh. It also emphasizes on the contribution of such establishments towards understanding the various aspects of Arunachal Tribes.

Methods

Data were collected from secondary sources and through interviewing with some Anthropologists and scholars from Arunachal Pradesh.

Discussion

Establishment of the Discipline

As mentioned, the beginning of Anthropological research in Arunachal Pradesh can be traced back to the pre-Independence period (Chaudhuri & Tayeng, 2015). However, the official recognition and introduction of the discipline in the state took place at the later stage. The introduction of Anthropology in the Arunachal Institute of Tribal Studies (AITS) as part of postgraduate academic programme in 2001 under Arunachal University (Now Rajiv Gandhi University, Doimukh) - which was established in 1984 - marked the formal beginning of the discipline in the State (Ramya, 2017). The institute operates as an interdisciplinary sector where scholars from various disciplines were attracted towards it for their research on the tribes. To this far, the AITS has already completed its 15th years of existence. Most of the researches on the tribes were undertaken by scholars at their MPhil and PhD research levels. However, ample amount of anthropological research projects was also undertaken (e.g. Behera, 1999; 2003). Anthropology in Arunachal University (now Rajiv Gandhi University) attained its status of a full-fledged independent department in 2012. The establishment of the Research Department, Department of Archaeology, Department of Cultural Affairs, Department of Linguistics under the Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh which

was established in 1951, however, marked a significant milestone towards the beginning and development of Anthropology in terms of the anthropological-oriented researches carried out prior to the establishment of AITS. These departments have undertaken and published good number of research reports, monographs, and papers through different levels of research and projects on different aspects of the tribes (Elwin, 1991; Deuri, 1982; Dutta, 2006).

Apart from these establishments, the introduction of Anthropology in the undergraduate courses at college level cannot be taken out of place. Saint Claret College, Ziro was the first and the only degree college to offer Anthropology in the undergraduate course since 2004. Other institutions offering anthropology includes Apex University, Pasighat (established in 2012) where anthropology is offered in both undergraduate and postgraduate level. Recently in 2015 and 2016, the discipline of anthropology was also introduced in Dera Natung Government College, Itanagar and Saint Francis De Sales College, Aalo respectively. However, the anthropology at Dera Natung Government College, Itanagar could start only in August 2018 with two guest faculties. The ground objective for the introduction of Anthropology in different educational institutions of the state was to open up a platform for learning, teaching, and research in various fields related to the various anthropological issues of the tribes in Arunachal Pradesh.

Contribution of the Establishments

Prior to the formal establishment of the discipline, the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh have long been studied by various agencies...the eminent administrators, the Anthropological Survey of India, the Research Department of NEFA (now Arunachal Pradesh), researchers, and social scientists (Goswami & Das, 1990). Nevertheless, significant number of empirical research contributions could be seen after the establishment of the department in various sectors. In the purview of this discussion, however, contribution of Anthropology towards understanding the Arunachal tribes - after the formal establishment - will be included; partly for reason of time and space but mainly on methodological grounds.

With the establishment of the Research Institutions & Departments, Arunachal Institute of Tribal Studies under Rajiv Gandhi University, Anthropology Departments in Colleges and Universities, and other institutions, many research contributions have been witnessed over time. Most of these researches took coverage of the social and cultural aspects of the tribes in connection to religion, economy, indigenous knowledge system & resource management, ethnomedicine, folklore, culture and identity, material culture, gender studies, etc. Little is known – though not completely absent – about

researches on language, physical-biological aspects of the tribes, genetic studies, studies on growth, health and nutrition. Reports of the studies were published in journals, proceedings, books, theses, and dissertations.

Monographs

The British administrators wrote a series of 16 monographs on the tribes of Assam, Manipur, and Nagaland between 1906 and 1937 under a well-organized scheme executed by the Directorate of Ethnography. However, it still remains to begin a similar work for the tribes of Arunachal in April 1957 (Vidyarthi, 1986). Of the later works that took place after the formal establishment of anthropology as a discipline in Universities, Government and Research Departments, includes those monographs published by scholars and professors at different times after 1984. The publications mostly covered ethnographic studies of the major tribes such as the Khambas (Dutta, 2006), the Mishmis (Cooper, 1973/1995), the Galos (Basar, 2006), the Nyishi and Khampti tribes (Behera, 2008), the Mijis (Chaudhuri, 2013), the Bangrus (Ramya, 2011; 2012), and more. In general, the monographs of the tribes reflect the social-cultural, language, belief system, subsistence patterns, political and economic affairs, etc. of the tribes.

Studies on Religion, Indigenous Faith and Practices

Some of the major works done on the religious aspects of the Arunachal tribes include researches on the sacred complexes (Behera, 1998, 2003, 2005; Drema, 2001), Shamanism (Miso, 2005; Potom, 2005), Revivalism (Rukbo, 2000; Showren, 2002, Ering, 1998; VKIC, 2005; Mihi, 2004), and impact of Christianity (Kach, 2002; Rikam, 2005; Chaudhuri, 2009; Riddi, 2009; Ramya, 2012). These studies were mainly carried out by the native researchers and scholars of Arunachal Pradesh, mostly on their respective tribe. The works of scholars such as Mibang & Chaudhuri (2003) on Ethno Medicines of the Tribes of Arunachal Pradesh, Phukan (2000) on the Spiritual Beliefs and Practices among the Arunachalees, and Rina (2001) on Conversion in Arunachal Pradesh: A Study with reference to crisis, etc., are of great significance and reflects the contribution of the Research Departments and Academic Institutions in the state towards the better understanding of the tribes.

Folklores

Various works on Folklores have been taken up under the Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh as well at the university level. Sharma (1988) published his work on the Essays on the Folklore of North Eastern India which is of tremendous help in understanding this aspect of the tribes of Northeast India. In 1990, Tayeng published his book describing the folk songs of the Adi tribe of Arunachal

Pradesh through the Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh. Datta, et al. (1994) published their study on the Folklore Materials of the Tribes of Northeast. The works of Mibang (1995) on Adi Dooying; Sen (2000), Mibang & Abraham (2002), Mibang & Chaudhuri (2004) on the Tradition and Folklore in North East India, Blackburn (2008), and Ramya (2013) on Tribal Culture and Folklore of Arunachal Pradesh, are of great benefits to the anthropological community of academicians and students. The tribes of Arunachal are seen to be culturally rich in terms of folklore tradition.

Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) and Resource Management

Most of the tribes of Arunachal are well known for their unique indigenous knowledge system and resource management that helps them for better survival and wellbeing. This close interaction of the tribes to their respective environmental settings is seen in various studies undertaken far back and recently. Some of the major works on this aspect includes that of – Ramakrishnan (1997), Singh (1991, 1997), Behera (1997), Dollo et al. (2009), Chaudhry et al. (2011), Basar (2011), Ramya (2013, 2014, 2016), and Pangging et al. (2016). There are of course many more recent publications on the IKS and resource management of the tribal groups of Arunachal. Most of those works were undertaken under the aegis of the Rajiv Gandhi University and the Directorate of Research.

Other Aspects of Culture

Culture comprises of numerous elements of human behaviours in terms of materials and nonmaterial aspects. Through the establishment of anthropology in various sectors of the state, there have been numerous contributions – to understanding these aspects – from the research community in the form of publications. Of those, the studies on the integration between culture and identity, culture and education, economic and development, women and gender studies, and the like are found prominent and significant in this regard.

Studies on the identity of the tribes by Patnaik (2006), Mibang & Behera (2007), Dawar (2003), Behera (2001), gives a reflection on the cultural identity and ownership of the tribes of various locations in the state. The understanding on the influence of education and other factors on human culture is also reflected through series of academic publications. Some of the major works undertaken under these areas includes that of Begi (2007), Behera (2002), Basar & Tok (2004).

Other aspects of culture such as economic, development, politics, and gender & women studies also took place in the last few years and mark the significant contribution of the establishment of anthropological units in various offices. Behera conducted his

studies – ICSSR/UGC projects – on the Impact of Orange Cultivation on the Role of Galo Women, Objective Assessment of Poverty Alleviation Programmes in Selected Villages of Arunachal Pradesh, and on the Socio-Economic Portents of Displacement of Indigenous Peoples in Arunachal Pradesh in 1999, 2003, and 2005 respectively.

Studies on gender and women have become integral in the field of anthropological research. Significant numbers of research have contributed towards the understanding of this issue. Of the many researches and projects undertaken under this theme, good numbers are found to be of high importance and contributively. Mibang & Abraham (2003) published their works on Arunachal Women & Education, Basar (2007) on Women's Movement in Arunachal Pradesh, Pandey (1997) on the General Status of Women in Tribal Society (through the Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh, Itanagar), Behera (2000) on theorizing gender inequality as social inequality in terms of sex-based division of labour and with reference to the tribal society, and Ramya (2017) on Factors behind Domestic Violence against Nyishi Women in Arunachal Pradesh.

Biological Anthropological Research

The beginning of physical anthropological research on the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh can be traced back to 1910s and attributed to the work of Brown and Kemp on the anthropometric measurements of the 84 Abor males and 10 Abor females (the Adis) of Arunachal Pradesh. Besides, other anthropometric investigations were also conducted with the basic aim of helping the British colonization through data analysis. Nevertheless, research works in the field of physical anthropology in Arunachal Pradesh are still few and limited till date.

The Government of Arunachal Pradesh (previously NEFA) initiated a research project entitled Anthropometric Survey of Arunachal People in 1970 under the aegis of University of Gauhati where Sri B. Das Shastri and Dr. P.C. Dutta – the then Director of Research and Deputy Director of Research respectively – took the lead. The project was mainly to study the physical anthropological variables of the people of Arunachal. The project, however, was expanded through deeper and rigorous collection of data under the heading Biogenetic Survey of the Arunachal People and continued till 1980. The data and findings of both the projects were later compiled by M. C. Goswami and P. B. Das as a report entitled *The People of Arunachal Pradesh: A Physical Survey* (Goswami & Das, 1990). It may be noted that this was the first extensive physical anthropological research on the seventeen major tribes of Arunachal Pradesh covering the various physical, biological, and genetic aspects - Anthropometry, Blood groups, PTC taste sensitivity, and Dermatoglyphics.

Duarah (1992) carried out an anthropometric study of the Monpas during the 1980s which was published in his book *The Monpas of Arunachal Pradesh*. Duarah put emphasis on the growth patterns of the Monpas at three altitudes viz., Kalaktang, Dirang and Tawang, with special reference to the growth of Monpa boys (between the age 8 to 17 years). However, physical anthropological variables – Morphological, Genetical, Behavioural and Dermatoglyphics – of the Monpa populations were also studied along with the aspects of physical variation.

Genetic studies on the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh were carried out at different times by different scholars. Kotal et al. (2003) reported their findings on the genetic markers of the Digaru Mishmis with respect to the distribution of ABO and Rh (D) blood group, PTC taste sensitivity and colour blindness. Other significant contributions in this field were made by Bhattacharjee (1954) an investigation on the blood group of the Abor (Adis); Bhattacharjee (1957) on the ABO, MN, and ABH secretion among the Noctes; Choudhury & Das (1974) and Choudhury (1978) on the frequency of colour blindness of some Arunachal populations; Das & Choudhury (1975) on the pattern of hand clasping, arm folding, earlobe attachment and colour blindness among the Gal-long; Duarah & Das (1978) on the genetic traits of the Tagins; Duarah (1979) on the distribution of ABO, MN and Rh blood groups among the Mishmis of Lohit; Duarah (1980) on the ABO blood groups and some genetic traits of the Sulung of Subansiri District; Kar (1975) on the Rh blood group among the Adis of Pasighat; Kumar (1955; 1975) on the Taste, Mid phalangeal and occipital hair whorls of the Nocte Nagas; and blood group and secretor frequency among the Gallong (now Galo). Srivastava (1971) also carried out a research on the PTC taste sensitivity of the tribes of NEFA.

Studies on the dermatoglyphic patterns of the Arunachalees indicate that the tribal populations of this part of the country (similar to the Naga groups and Maria Muslims of Assam) depict maximum value of Furuhat's Index (Sengupta, 2003). In addition, dermatoglyphic studies on the tribes of Arunachal were also studied by different scholars at different times. Some of the significant works include those studies on Gallongs (now Galo), Hill Miris (now Nyishi), Idu Mishmis, Kalaktang Monpas, Khamtis, Khowa, Mijis (now Sajolang), Miju Mishmis, Minyongs, Nyishis, Noctes, Padam, Sherdukpens, Singphos, Tagin, Tangsas, Tawang Monpas, and Wangchos (Kumar, 1975; Bhattacharjee, 1955; Sharma, 1962; Chakraborty & Mukherjee, 1961; Dutta, 1973 & 1977; Das, 1980, Dutta and Sengupta, 1983; Sengupta, 1984; Das et al., 1985; Jaswal et al., 1986; and Goswami & Das, 1990).

With regards to Dental Anthropological research, it may be pointed that limited research works were carried out in this part of the country. Limbu (1990) reported an incidence of periodontal disease among the Gallong (now Galo) to be 73.98 %. In 1996, he reported his findings on the age and sequence of permanent teeth emergence among the Gallong (now Galo) children of Arunachal. However, more research is necessary to be carried out with respect to understanding the dental patterns of the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh.

Research on Language and Oral Traditions

The visual of oral tradition is very diverse in Arunachal Pradesh as almost 66 dialects are spoken. However, the whole structure of the linguistic diversity of the state is based on verbal form as only a few of the tribes (e.g., the Khamptis, Monpas, Sherdukpens, etc.) have their own scripts (Singh, 1995). Unfortunately, there are very few studies on the oral traditions of the people of Arunachal Pradesh. Even so, the first significant work on the oral tradition of our state is that of Verrier Elwin. Elwin has done some notable works - *Myths of North East Frontier of India* (1958/1999) and *A New Book on Tribal Fiction* (1970). The *Myths of North East Frontier of India* includes nearly 400 myths collected from all over Arunachal Pradesh from 1954 to 1957 and *A New Book on Tribal Fiction* includes the fairy tales of the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh which gives a brief glimpse of the institutions of slavery, village councils, barter trade, etc.

In addition, studies on the diversity of languages of the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh were also taken up by other young researchers. Dondrup (1988), for instance, wrote on the language of the Sherdukpens of South-West Kameng District of Arunachal Pradesh; Megu (2003) reported his study on the language of Aashings, a sub-group of the Adi community; Rekhung (1988) on the language of the Lungchangs, a sub-tribe of the Tangsa who lives in Tirap district of Arunachal Pradesh, etc.

Nevertheless, there are other written works on the Linguistics and oral traditions of tribes of Arunachal Pradesh by various researchers and anthropologists. The Directorate of Research under the Department of Cultural Affairs, Government of Arunachal Pradesh is a pioneer organisation which works on the languages of majority of tribes (Banerjee, 1996; Barauh, 1998; Dutta, 1990; Giri, 2013; Sarkar, 1999; Sinha, 1998). The reports were published in the forms of books on phrase, tales, dictionaries, etc. The District Gazetteers contribution through published and unpublished research works also gives some lights on the understanding of the tribes' oral traditions.

However, despite all richness, not all works illustrate the overall picture of oral traditions of the communities inhabiting the state. Apart from few dictionaries and grammars, very few works are available on proverbs, myths and tales, songs, etc., which are limited to only 2 or 3 tribes. There is a total silence on the oral traditions of other groups (Sharma, 2012).

Archaeological Research

Since the early part of the 19th century, several British scholars and experts in Earth, Life and Social Sciences were deputed to this part of India to carry out systematic investigations on the natural resources and human variability (Sharma, 1980). Archaeological investigations in Arunachal Pradesh have been carried out by different scholars and institutions since pre-independence and had documented number of prehistoric tools, sites, pottery, monuments and other artefacts. The state has at present seven protected and large number of unprotected archaeological sites (Tada, 2014).

Some of the pioneer organizations - The Archaeological survey of India, Directorate of Research, Government of Arunachal Pradesh - play an important role in the exploration, excavation and conservation of the sites and monuments. The archaeological data so far available from the different parts of the state indicates the archaeological richness of this place and also throws light on the better understanding of the beginning of human society's right from the prehistoric times – which can be traced back to the 10th-12th century AD – and the migration route of the early inhabitants of this place.

Data on prehistoric archaeology of Arunachal Pradesh is still meagre. The 19th century scholar Lubbock (1867) reported a light green Neolithic Celt from Namsang in Tirap district. More Neolithic Celts were also reported by E. H. Steel from the same area of Namsang in 1870 (Steel, 1870). In 1871, John Anderson reported the discovery of a Neolithic Celt from the Mishmi Hills (Anderson, 1871). Later, R. D. Banerjee (1924-25), the first Indian Archaeologist to explore the prehistoric remains of Arunachal, described a stone adze found in the Abor Hills in Meiso village on the left bank of Dihong River. Good numbers of artefacts which were found from this region are now preserved in Pitt Rivers Museum, Oxford. The implements were collected by J. P. Mills and J. H. Grace between 1933 and 1935 (Dani, 1960). Tools and artefacts of Arunachal Neolithic were also reported from other tribal inhabited areas of the state. Neolithic Celts were reported from areas inhabited by the Sulungs (Stonor, 1952). Three triangular ground axes and one polished broken Celts were reported from Bhismanagar (Raikar & Chatterjee, 1980). Goswami (1972) along with his colleagues reported a collection of 18 Neolithic Celts from the Kameng district of Arunachal Pradesh which comprises of Shouldered

Celts, trapeze, triangular and splayed axes. In 1969-70, the Geological Survey of India in collaboration with the Anthropological, Archaeological, Botanical and Zoological Surveys led a joint expedition in the Daphabum area of Lohit district under the lead of B. P. Bopardikar (IAR 1969-70; Bopardikar, 1972). As a result of this project, three sites, viz. Kale, Teehum, and Glow were found that yielded varieties of artefacts belonging to the Pre-Neolithic and Neolithic phase of Stone Age culture in Arunachal. The excavation, though not conclusive, suggests the possibility of existence and discovering Pre-historic tools in Arunachal Pradesh.

Another noteworthy survey in the field of archaeology in Arunachal Pradesh was that reported by Duarah (1979) on the Neolithic Celts and an excavation reported by A. A. Ashraf exploring the various parts of Kamla and Kurung valleys since 1982. This exploration resulted in the discovery of the Neolithic site known as Parsi-Parlo (Ashraf, 1990). Sarkar (1982) reported 12 Celts and broken Celts collected from different parts of the state.

An extensive exploration in 1994-95 under the aegis of the Directorate of Research, Arunachal Pradesh (IAR 1995-96) around Daporijo revealed the Neolithic culture of that area, after having found few artefacts on the surface (documented at Archaeological Survey of India, Nagpur). In addition, a few stone artefacts (now preserved in State Museum, Itanagar) were collected in 2010 from Leel village of Kurung Kumey District.

Concluding Remarks

Apart from the above-mentioned researches and publications, however, taking into consideration of the broad scope of Anthropology as a discipline, it appears that though the establishment of the discipline at different levels of sectors took place, there is a need of wider coverage of studies in terms of research, projects, and publications. Anthropology as a holistic study of human beings gives explanation of every aspects of human kind - their social, cultural as well as biological aspects. To this end, most researches and studies conducted falls by and large under the horizon of social-cultural anthropology. Researches in the field of biological anthropology, genetics, growth, nutrition and health are still limited. It may be mentioned that, until 2012 when the Department of Anthropology attained its full status as a full-fledged discipline in Rajiv Gandhi University, the discipline was ran under the Arunachal Institute of Tribal Studies (AITS). The Institute of Tribal Studies mainly focuses on the researches and studies related to culture, behaviour, religion, political organization, and economic status of the tribes of Arunachal Pradesh. Researches on the aspects of language, physical make up,

genetics, growth, nutrition, and health aspects of the tribal populations of Arunachal are yet to be further explored.

Therefore, there is a need of expanding the scope and objective, the areas of research to be taken up at various levels of standard, i.e., in the undergraduate level, post graduate, MPhil and PhD level, minor and major projects to be taken up by the Departments of Research, Universities, Colleges, and other Institutions. There is also a need of support from government, collaboration between educational institutions and funding agencies (e.g., ICSSR, ICMR, AnSI, ASI, etc.), Language Department, Archaeological Department, and the like.

It may be concluded, however, that the beginning and growth of Anthropology in this part of the country – through its establishment – has open up a wide range of research interests among academicians, researchers, students, policy makers etc. However, there is always a scope for improvement; a scope of improving the dimensions of Anthropology as a relevant research & academic discipline in Arunachal Pradesh; the scope of broadening its dimensions through addressing new research questions, formulation of hypotheses, and through standard conduct of empirical researches.

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